

VTT

Hybrid Gasification-Synthesis Process with CO₂ Recycling to Improve Synthetic Fuels Yield and Carbon Efficiency – Techno-economic Assessment

**Sanna Tuomi, Esa Kurkela, Minna Kurkela, Ilkka
Hiltunen**

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Biomass gasification for biofuels and bio-chemicals

- Long experience of medium-to-large scale synthesis gas technologies

1985

1995

2000

2005

2010

2015

2020

2025

2030

COAL GASIFIER
APPLIED FOR
PEAT AND WOOD

LARGE-SCALE GASIFICATION
SPECIALLY DEVELOPED
FOR WOOD FEEDSTOCKS

PROCESS DEVELOPMENT FOR
LOWER CAPEX, HIGHER CARBON
UTILIZATION AND WASTES

Key steps in the gasification-synfuels process of VTT

Technological basis – TRL7

- Air-blown CFB gasifier commercial, **steam/O₂-blown demonstrated at 12 MW**
- Filtration demonstrated at 5 MW scale, commercial in air-blown gasification
- **Reforming demonstrated at 5 MW scale**
- Final gas cleaning commercial (similar to coal gasification)

Methanol production from biomass

BASE CASE – Biomass alone, H₂/CO molar ratio adjusted with a shift unit

Methanol production from biomass

HYBRID 1 – CO shift replaced with electrolysis H₂

Methanol production from biomass

HYBRID 2 – CO₂ recycling to increase the use of external H₂

Methanol production from biomass

HYBRID 3 – Electrolyser dimensioned to produce all oxygen consumed at the plant

VTT's pressurized O₂/steam-blown CFB gasification pilot plant at Bioruukki

CFB gasifier "UCG2021"

Plant capacity, MW	0.2-0.5
Operation pressure, bar	1 - 8
Temperature range, °C	750 - 920
Gasification agents	Air, O ₂ + Steam/CO ₂
Feedstocks	Biomass residues, wastes
Feed rate, kg/h	max. 100 kg/h
Gas velocities, m/s	
Fluidizing velocity at the bottom of bed	1 - 3
Gas velocity at the top of reactor	1.5 - 3
Reactor (i.d.), mm	
Lower part	150
Upper part	225
Reactor height, m	
Total height	7.5

Total gasification hours ~5000 h (CFB gasification, hot filter and reformer)

Preliminary testing of CO₂ recycling in VTT's gasification pilot with forest residues

Wet gas composition after catalytic reforming

Preliminary testing of CO₂ recycling in VTT's gasification pilot with forest residues

Tar and benzene concentrations after reforming

Set point
Feedstock
Reformer II (out), °C
Reformer III (out), °C

Preliminary testing of CO₂ recycling in VTT's gasification pilot with forest residues

Tar and benzene concentrations after gasifier

C_{conv}
96-97%

Set point
Feedstock
Gasifier (top), °C
Gasifier (bed), °C

Estimated energy balances and efficiencies for MeOH production from forest residue feedstock

ELE, MW	-	32.9	67.7	69.9
CO ₂ rec, %	-	-	33	35
Steam repl, %	-	-	50	53

- **Feedstock:** Forest residues (50 wt-% moisture as received, dried to 12 wt-%)
- **Steam/O₂ CFB gasification:** 880 °C, 4 bar
- **Filtration:** 550 °C
- **Catalytic reforming:** outlet temperature 900 °C
- **MeOH synthesis:** 260 °C, 80 bar

Estimated distribution of feedstock carbon

Estimated production cost of methanol

- CASE 1 (Base case)
- CASE 2 (ELE replacing WGS)
- ▲ CASE 3 (ELE + CO2 recycling)
- ▲ CASE 4 (ELE + CO2 recycling, ASU replaced)

- Price of feedstock 20 €/MWh
- Price of electricity 45 €/MWh
- Value of heat 40 €/MWh
- Interest rate 7%
- Economic life of plant 20 a

Conclusions

- Hybrid gasification-synthesis process with CO₂ recycling to the gasifier and the reformer (to replace part of the steam feed) is estimated to have significant potential in improving synthetic fuels yield, process efficiency and carbon efficiency.
- Preliminary experimental work in steam/oxygen-blown CFB gasification conditions would suggest that replacing 50% of the steam feed in the gasifier and the catalytic reformer would not compromise gasifier/reformer performance. However, more extensive testing and especially long-term runs are needed to verify this assumption and the technical limitations for CO₂ recycling.
- In methanol production from biomass, hybrid concepts that couple gasification with electrolysis are estimated to be economically attractive already with current electricity price levels. CO₂ recycling has the potential for further cost reductions especially with lower electricity prices.

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the obvious

Sanna Tuomi
sanna.tuomi@vtt.fi
+358 40 357 9238

@VTTFinland
[www.vttresearch.com/en/ourservices/
thermochemical-conversion](http://www.vttresearch.com/en/ourservices/thermochemical-conversion)

www.vtt.fi

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